

DUNE IN THE CONTEXT OF LAS4RI. THE COLOMBIAN CASE

Thematic Areas

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Abstract

Thanks to past European and American initiatives, Latin American countries have an active presence in large scientific collaborations and, as a consequence, the scientific community is ready to transfer the knowledge gained to the local industry in order to contribute to the development of our countries and their people. The participation of Colombian institutions in the development of the DUNE experiment is an example of how Latin American countries can help designing one mega-science experiment. This document summarizes the Colombian activities in the design of the photon detection system of the DUNE experiment and presents the perspectives for the future regional working around the project.

Introduction

Knowledge is gaining greater added value for industrial and economic sectors, today, research is viewed as a tool for solving social, economic and political problems.¹ Research in basic science has demonstrated the central role in cutting edge technologies around the world, in that way the relationship between specific academic results and the industry has been demonstrated for decades.² It is well established from the experience obtained by Latin American countries in multiple collaborations in the United States and Europe, the importance of participating continuously in the investigation at the physics frontier. Cooperation in these projects offers direct products for the industry and access to new technology for the groups involved, however, the impact of these developments on the local industry is difficult to predict.³ Increasing the ability to transform specific knowledge into useful methods to keep the local industry competitive based on basic research is important for the Latin American scientific community.

However, an active participation in such investigative tasks demands a long-term budget from government agencies that allows scientists to acquire bigger commitments and, longer-term engagements. Despite each country's efforts, a methodology of cooperative work between Latin American countries is needed, which allows greater technological transfer to the region.⁴

Scientific Context

The Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment (DUNE) is one of the most ambitious and promising experiments currently under construction. The experiment's main focus lies in the area of neutrino physics as well as nucleon decay. In the neutrino sector DUNE will look for signs of CP violation, put constraints on the neutrino mass hierarchy, and improve some of the parameters related to neutrino physics. For proton decay, DUNE will have unprecedented sensitivity to the decay of a proton into a charged kaon and an antineutrino, although it is possible to study some other nucleon decay modes as well.

¹ Mueller, P. (2006). Exploring the knowledge filter: How entrepreneurship and university–industry relationships drive economic growth. *Research policy*, 35(10), 1499-1508.

² Lendel, I. (2010). The impact of research universities on regional economies: The concept of university products. *Economic Development Quarterly*, 24(3), 210-230.

³ Lynn, G. S., Abel, K. D., Valentine, W. S., & Wright, R. C. (1999). Key factors in increasing speed to market and improving new product success rates. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 28(4), 319-326.

⁴ Ponds, R., Oort, F. V., & Frenken, K. (2009). Innovation, spillovers and university–industry collaboration: an extended knowledge production function approach. *Journal of Economic Geography*, 10(2), 231-255.

DUNE has an ancillary program that goes beyond the aforementioned goals. Due to the great potential of the experiment, it is possible to study and constrain physics beyond the Standard Model (BSM). For instance, DUNE could be sensitive to deviations of the neutrino standard interactions, which arise from BSM physics. Moreover, due to the high-intensity proton beam used by the experiment, it is possible to produce BSM particles that could then be detected in the near detector, those particles could be part of a dark sector or could be dark matter candidates themselves. Colombian institutions are also working on this front, developing models as well as effective theories to understand the experiment's sensitivity to new physics signals.

Given that DUNE is a mega-science project, it requires contributions from many countries from all over the world. Currently, more than 2000 scientists from over 30 countries are involved in the development of the experiment. Latin American countries are actively involved in the photon detection system (PDS) for the single-phase far detector. The PDS system, together with the time projection chamber (TPC) system will allow for event time reconstruction which is crucial for several of the scientific goals of the experiment. We are aware of the opportunities for the Latin American industry to take an advance on the technology under development at this time, specifically, in the PDS because of the direct engineering applications, in the energetic and financial sectors.

Objectives

- Keep research and innovation policy on the political agenda.⁵ This is the main purpose of the present effort, because it is the correct mechanism to gather the budget and the economical conditions to develop many experiments in the upcoming years.
- Find and create communication channels for translating new research into industry. The approval of economic support comes with a reasonable social responsibility. We must find ways to transfer scientific knowledge into industry. One mechanism could be by demanding that researchers do internships in the industrial sector. Through these internships, researchers must solve practical problems. Examples of successful application of this methodology are found in data science, chemistry, industrial processes optimization, material sciences, etc.

⁵ Pingfang, Z., & Weimin, X. (2003). On The Impact of Government's S&T Incentive Policy on the R&D input and its patent output of large and medium-sized Industrial enterprises in Shanghai [J]. *Economic Research Journal*, 6, 45-53.

- The transference must be preferent for startups rather than big industries.⁶ This is because startups are more dynamical at innovation. By their very nature, they are more prone to use new technologies, and apply them. Moreover, their economy is more suitable for generating added value with less expenses than big industries.
- Promote and strengthen the transfer of technologies at the regional level.⁷ At the Latin American level there is now a critical number of researchers in order to create a scientific community that could solve academic and social problems. We have to find the appropriate channels for promoting communication among researchers at different levels.

Methodology

The participation on the DUNE experiment is an unprecedented opportunity to make a contribution of great responsibility at the regional level; also to understand the challenges related to community work. We must find the mechanisms to link research in basic science to the productive and industrial sector through concrete strategies that places responsibilities on both sectors.

Having a long-term budget is a general objective for the entire scientific community with the purpose of acquiring long-term responsibilities in large experiments, without the migration of qualified personal. Enhancement of the communication channels between groups involved in the same experiment is mandatory for the sake of allocation and management of the available resources.

It is needed to find a critical mass of people beyond experts, interested in high energy physics, to link other areas of knowledge that can communicate with the industry, like engineers, economists and mathematicians, with the responsibility of communicating with the industry in order to enable the added value of basic research in technology.⁸

⁶ Cohen, W. M., Nelson, R. R., & Walsh, J. P. (2002). Links and impacts: the influence of public research on industrial R&D. *Management science*, 48(1), 1-23.

⁷ Mueller, P. (2006). Exploring the knowledge filter: How entrepreneurship and university–industry relationships drive economic growth. *Research policy*, 35(10), 1499-1508.

⁸ High-level round table on the ADDED VALUE OF EXCELLENCE IN EUROPEAN RESEARCH 6 – 7 March 2017 · Brussels

Additionally we propose the following strategies:

- Holding meetings that promote participation at different levels with discussions focused on technology transfer and variety of consultancy, research hiring, and joint research^{9 10}.
- Moreover, we must develop a training program for researchers to find the social problems that need solutions where they can apply the acquired knowledge is needed to find the critical number of people beyond experts, interested in high energy physics, to link other areas of knowledge that can communicate with the industry, like engineers, economists and mathematicians, with the responsibility of communicating with the industry in order to enable the add value of tech.¹¹

List of the interested scientists in the community

At today, four colombian institutions belong to the DUNE collaboration. The institutions are Universidad del Atlantico, Universidad EIA, Universidad Antonio Narino (UAN) and Universidad Sergio Arboleda. From the already mentioned institutions EIA and UAN are working directly in the design of digitalization boards for the Photon Detection system of DUNE. It is expected that the Universidad de Antioquia joins this effort in the near future.

Current status and expected challenges

DUNE is the first science project of this scale in the USA that will be built under an international collaboration scheme. This opens a series of opportunities for countries around the world to participate in the design and construction of specific components gaining experience and strengthen relationships with the local industry. In particular, Colombia is working in the designing of the digitalization boards of the Photon Detector system. As a result of this work at the beginning of the year 2020, the production of a small number of prototypes board is planned. The prototypes will be tested at different facilities around the world with the close collaboration between Colombian, Peruvian and Paraguayan engineers.

⁹ D'Este, P., & Patel, P. (2007). University–industry linkages in the UK: What are the factors underlying the variety of interactions with industry?. *Research policy*, 36(9), 1295-1313.

¹⁰ Cohen, W. M., Nelson, R. R., & Walsh, J. P. (2002). Links and impacts: the influence of public research on industrial R&D. *Management science*, 48(1), 1-23.

¹¹ High-level round table on the ADDED VALUE OF EXCELLENCE IN EUROPEAN RESEARCH 6 – 7 March 2017 · Brussels

An experiment of this size sets important challenges related to the physics goals and the use of a large TPC, technology very well tested in relatively small sizes. For example, the experiment needs to be sensitive to a broad range of energies, from the low energy of the supernova events to energetic neutrinos coming from the galactic core. The event size of different processes from one event in the case of proton decay to millions of in the case of beam neutrinos demands the development of a trigger system with internal and external inputs. Reconstruction of liquid argon data is complex and requires novel algorithms based on machine learning techniques and using important computational resources.

In the case of the Photon detector system, precise timing and energy calibration imply the use of fast electronics components in a board to comply with the budget limitations and the requirements that the physics goals demand. The dimmer light coming from the most faraway region of the TPC needs to be collected, for that reason a large photon collection is required at the far end with the use of a new technology developed in Brazil.

The PDS includes a light collection system, light sensors, readout electronics, and monitoring systems. The light Collection is based on the so-called ARAPUCA concept which consists of the trapping of photons in a box with highly reflective internal surfaces. Inside of each ARAPUCA, 48 Silicon Photomultipliers (SiPM) will be connected to detect the trapped photons. The exact type of SiPM, mounting and connection scheme is under investigation.

To read the SiPMs signals, digitalization at room temperature will be performed by electronics boards currently under design by Colombian engineers in collaboration with Fermilab. The boards are known as DAPHNE (Detector Electronic for Acquiring Photons from Neutrinos) and will be in charge of the digitalization, initial processing and communication of the PDS with the DAQ system.

Timeline

The first DUNE SP module is planned to be ready by the year 2024, the TDR will be delivered at the end of 2019 with a defined detector strategy but still, after that time an intensive work has to be done to prepare the subsystems production and to complete details related with the data collecting and analyzing. Two examples of small scale prototypes are ProtoDUNE located at CERN and the ICEBERG facility test in Fermilab.

Fine-tuning of the technologies and data rates expected in the detector can be extrapolated from data taking at the prototypes.

The expected general timeline is:

2021: Test of DAPHNE boards at ProtoDUNE II

2024: Start installing first SP module

2025: Start installing the second module and DUNE physics with atmospheric neutrinos.

2026: Beam operation at 1.2 MW

2027: Add third FD Module

2029: Add fourth FD Module

2032: Upgrade to 2.4 MW beam

Construction and operational costs

The final design of the DUNE experiment is still under discussion. In particular, the Photon detection system is planned to have a total cost of production of 17 million U.S dollars. The digitalization electronics of the photon detector system are calculated of the order of 400000 US Dollars.

Discussion about a common fund is ongoing a fee per member and for a to be determined scale of time is considered. The initial proposal is the 10000 US Dollar yearly per member.